

Deliverable D5.2 Maintenance plan for ontology sustainability

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIA	BioImage Archive
ChEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest Ontology
CL	Cell Ontology
CLO	Cell Line Ontology
CMPO	Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology
DOID	Human Disease Ontology
EDAM	EMBRACE Data and Methods ontology
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
GerBI	German BioImaging
GO	Gene Ontology
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
IDR	Image Data Resource
MONDO	Mondo Disease Ontology
NCBITaxon	NCBI organismal classification

OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies
ODK	Ontology Development Kit
OLS	Ontology Lookup Service
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OxO	Ontology Xref Service
REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
ROR	Research Organization Registry
RRID	Research Resource Identifier
SSBD	A platform for Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
UBERON	Uberon Multi-species Anatomy Ontology
UO	Units of Measurement Ontology
UniProt	Universal Protein Resource

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Executive Summary

An interoperable global image data ecosystem depends on the ability to standardise metadata vocabularies. However, the ontologies and controlled vocabularies on which GIDE resources rely must continue to be maintained, and to grow as imaging techniques and scientific methods advance. This deliverable sets out how the selected ontology set will be supported towards long-term sustainability, and who will coordinate the updates and changes needed to keep it fit for purpose.

The plan takes as its starting point the ontology set recommended in D2.1, the harmonised representation specified in D6.1, and the implementation within resources reported in D5.1. It distinguishes two situations. The Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi) is the one element of the selected set specific to the bioimaging domain, and the one that required intervention during the project. It has now been returned to active, community-governed maintenance, and this deliverable describes ongoing arrangement for that maintenance. The remaining vocabularies are maintained by established external communities, and for these the plan describes a lighter model of monitoring and periodic review by GIDE resources of maintenance status.

For FBbi, maintenance is led by German BioImaging as a community effort under the foundingGIDE umbrella, with EMBL-EBI and RIKEN supporting the work. New term requests typically arise by one of three routes: requests raised by the maintainers, support for depositors who need a term that does not yet exist, and dedicated community events such as workshops and hackathons.

A per-ontology summary of these arrangements is given in Table 1, recording for each vocabulary its role in the shared GIDE bioimaging framework (of D6.1), its maintainer, the route by which the project and its community contribute terms, and the cadence at which the GIDE partners will review its place in the framework. This maintenance plan feeds into the project sustainability plan (D1.4), which sets the wider context for sustaining foundingGIDE outputs beyond the funded period.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

For the partner resources to describe image data with a shared vocabulary, that vocabulary has to remain available and current. An ontology that is not maintained gradually loses value: it cannot describe new imaging techniques as they emerge, its identifiers risk becoming unresolvable, and the annotations that depend on it drift out of step with practice. The work of selecting and implementing a shared set, reported in D2.1, D6.1 and D5.1, therefore needs to be matched by an arrangement for keeping that set maintained over time.

This deliverable sets out that arrangement. It covers two things. First, it describes how the chosen ontologies will continue to be maintained beyond the project, distinguishing the one ontology the project has taken into active maintenance, FBbi, from the wider set maintained by external communities. Second, it identifies who coordinates updates and changes for each, and the routes by which new and revised terms reach them. It does not re-derive the selected set or its representation, which are the subject of D2.1 and D6.1, nor does it repeat the implementation work reported in D5.1; it is concerned specifically with sustainability.

1.2 Relationship to other deliverables and out of scope topics

This deliverable sits at the sustainability end of the WP2, WP5 and WP6 workstream, and is best read alongside those outputs. It reports the maintenance plan for the selected ontologies in line with Task 5.3.

D2.1 provides the landscape analysis and the recommendation of the imaging ontology set whose sustainability is addressed here. D6.1 sets out the overlaps and gaps between the metadata models of the BioImage Archive, IDR and SSBD and the recommended representation for each metadata component through a systematic metadata comparison and ontology mapping across the three resources. That analysis identified the lapse in FBbi maintenance as a specific, and important risk and provided the evidence base that motivated the maintenance activities described here; it also surfaced the licensing constraints affecting some clinical vocabularies. The selection and harmonisation recommendations developed in D6.1 thus form part of the basis for both the implementation reported in D5.1 and the sustainability plan set out here.

This maintenance plan feeds into the project sustainability plan (D1.4), which addresses the long-term sustenance of foundingGIDE outputs as a whole and the associated risks and mitigations at project level. Preclinical imaging ontologies are addressed under Task 5.1 and reported in D4.1, and are outside the scope of this deliverable.

2. Approach to sustainability

2.1 Reusing community-maintained resources

The selected set was chosen, in D2.1, for its grounding in openly maintained community resources wherever possible. That choice carries directly into the approach to sustainability: the project's default position is to reuse ontologies and controlled vocabularies that are already maintained by established communities, rather than to take on maintenance itself. Resources such as NCBITaxon, the Cell Ontology, ChEBI, UBERON, the Units of Measurement Ontology and the disease vocabularies are developed and curated by communities with both the domain expertise and the supporting infrastructure to sustain them, and are used far beyond bioimaging. Duplicating that effort would be neither practical nor desirable; the project's contribution is better spent monitoring these resources, adopting their updates, and feeding bioimaging requirements back to them where gaps appear.

Active maintenance by the GIDE consortium is therefore the exception, reserved for the case where the bioimaging community carries a particular responsibility that no other community fills. FBbi is that case. It is the vocabulary specific to the bioimaging domain rather than one borrowed from an adjacent field, it is used across all three partner resources, and it was the one element of the selected set whose maintenance had lapsed and for which no external community was positioned to resume it. This lapse was identified explicitly through the metadata comparison and ontology mapping carried out by RIKEN under WP6, documented in the [accompanying mapping spreadsheet](#) and reflected in D6.1, which gave the consortium clear evidence to act. Returning FBbi to active maintenance, rather than substituting a complementary resource, preserved the existing annotations and tooling that depend on it and kept the method vocabulary within a community-governed OBO ontology.

2.2 Maintenance approach

The selected set divides into two cases, one of which applies to almost all of it and one of which, by design, applies to a single ontology.

For most of the selected vocabularies, which are maintained by established external communities, the consortium's role is monitoring and adoption. The consortium does not maintain these, but it does not treat them as fixed either. Their maintenance status is reviewed periodically, their releases are tracked so that the participating resources can adopt updates, and where the bioimaging community identifies a missing or inadequate term the project raises it with the maintaining community through that resource's own contribution process. Should a vocabulary in this group lapse or cease to meet the ecosystem's needs, the consortium follows the set of responses described in Section 3.2, the same logic D6.1 applied when it flagged the FBbi gap and raised complementary resources as a contingency.

FBbi is the exception, and the consortium expects it to remain the only one. Here the GIDE partners take on active maintenance: including the release process, the contribution channels and the addition and revision of terms. This is a deliberately narrow commitment. Active maintenance is more demanding than monitoring, and the consortium takes it on only because FBbi is the bioimaging-specific vocabulary at the centre of the ecosystem and had no other community sustaining it. Should another bioimaging-specific vocabulary fall into the same position, the same

approach could be extended to it, but the intention is to return resources to external community maintenance wherever a suitable community exists, not to accumulate maintenance responsibilities.

2.3 Routes for contributing terms

In both cases new and revised terms typically reach an ontology through three complementary routes, used according to where the need arises and who is best placed to act on it.

The first is **maintainer-led requests**: the maintainers of an actively-maintained ontology, or the project members tracking an externally-maintained one, identify a gap through their own curation work or through resource implementation and raise it directly. The second is **support for depositors**: when a submitter to one of the participating resources needs a term that does not yet exist, the resource helps them describe the proposed term and routes the request to the relevant ontology. The third is **organised community events**: workshops, hackathons and similar gatherings, including those supported by this project, are used to work through larger batches of terms or more substantial revisions with community domain experts present. These routes are not mutually exclusive; a single coverage gap may be raised by a depositor, triaged by the maintainers and resolved at a subsequent event.

3. Maintenance arrangements

3.1 Active maintenance of FBbi

The Biological Imaging Methods Ontology is, from 2026 onwards, maintained as a joint community effort under the umbrella of the GIDE consortium. Maintenance is led by German BioImaging (see https://gerbi-gmb.de/2026/02/06/bi_methods_ontology/), with EMBL-EBI and RIKEN supporting the work and able to share or take on load as needed, so that the arrangement does not rest on a single point of failure. The source files are held in a public repository at <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/fbbi> under a CC-BY-4.0 licence, and the ontology continues to be served through the established OBO Foundry channels: the stable release is available at the persistent identifier <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/fbbi.owl>, and terms can be browsed in the EBI Ontology Lookup Service.

The repository is built using the Ontology Development Kit, the standard tooling for OBO ontologies, which provides a reproducible release process and aligns FBbi with the practices of the wider ontology community. Term addition and revision are managed through requests raised on the repository's issue tracker. This is the maintenance arrangement reported as established in D5.1, and it is the model this deliverable commits to sustaining; the question of how the underlying effort is resourced beyond the funded period is taken up in the project sustainability plan (D1.4).

3.2 Monitoring and periodic review of the wider selected set

For the vocabularies maintained by external communities, the GIDE bioimaging consortium members will maintain the list of vocabularies, not the vocabularies themselves. The participating resources will hold the selected set as a publicly available shared list and will review it periodically, on an annual cadence, checking for each vocabulary that it remains actively maintained, that its identifiers continue to resolve, and that its coverage still meets the needs of the ecosystem's submissions. Routine releases will be tracked between reviews so that the resources can take up new terms as they appear.

Where a review finds that a vocabulary no longer meets those conditions, the consortium will take two approaches to resolution. The first response is to engage with the maintaining community, contributing the missing terms or maintenance effort through that resource's own process. Where a vocabulary has lapsed and that engagement is not possible, the consortium will identify a complementary or successor resource already used in the ecosystem, as D6.1 noted when it raised alternatives against the risk of continued FBbi inactivity.

3.3 Maintenance and contribution arrangements by ontology

Table 1 summarises the arrangement for each ontology and controlled vocabulary in the selected set: its role in the harmonised framework, the community or organisation that maintains it, the route by which the project and its community contribute terms, and the cadence at which its maintenance status is reviewed. The review cadence is the project-side monitoring interval and is independent of each resource's own release schedule. Identifier schemes used purely for researchers, organisations and resources (ORCID, ROR, RRID) are omitted, as they are registries rather than ontologies requiring term-level maintenance.

Table 1: Maintenance and contribution arrangements for the selected ontology set.

Ontology vocabulary	Role in framework	Maintainer	Contribution route	Review cadence
FBbi	Imaging method; channel content	GerBI (lead), with EMBL-EBI and RIKEN support	Active maintenance: issue tracker, depositor support, community events, image.sc	Continuous (actively maintained);
NCBITaxon	Organism	NCBI	Monitor and adopt; requests via NCBI process	Annual
CL	Cell type	OBO community (CL maintainers)	Monitor and adopt; requests via CL issue tracker	Annual
CLO	Cell line	OBO community (CLO maintainers)	Monitor and adopt;	Annual

Ontology vocabulary /	Role in framework	Maintainer	Contribution route	Review cadence
			depositor-driven requests upstream	
ChEBI	Compound	EMBL-EBI (ChEBI team)	Monitor and adopt; requests via ChEBI submission process	Annual
EFO	Experimental condition; broader entities	EMBL-EBI (EFO team)	Monitor and adopt; requests via EFO issue tracker	Annual
UBERON	Anatomy / organ	OBO community (Uberon maintainers)	Monitor and adopt; requests via Uberon issue tracker	Annual
UO	Units	OBO community (UO maintainers)	Monitor and adopt; requests via UO issue tracker	Annual
MONDO	Disease (with linkage to DOID, ICD-11)	Mondo / Monarch Initiative	Monitor and adopt; requests via Mondo issue tracker	Annual
CMPO	Phenotype	EMBL-EBI (CMPO maintainers)	Monitor and adopt; depositor-driven requests upstream	Annual

Ontology vocabulary /	Role in framework	Maintainer	Contribution route	Review cadence
EDAM	Image analysis technique descriptions	EDAM community	Monitor and adopt; requests via EDAM process	Annual
UniProt	Protein	EMBL-EBI (UniProt)	Database accession; resolves in source database, no term maintenance by project	Annual (status check)
Ensembl	Gene	EMBL-EBI (Ensembl)	Database accession; resolves in source database, no term maintenance by project	Annual (status check)

3.4 Roles of the participating resources

The three resources contribute to maintenance in complementary ways. RIKEN led the metadata comparison and ontology mapping under WP6 that underpins the selected set and first identified the FBbi maintenance gap; through SSBD it supports FBbi maintenance and feeds requirements arising from SSBD submissions. GerBI-OME leads FBbi maintenance and, in its role offering guidance on future compatibility with the IDR, helps ensure the maintained set remains usable by that resource as it evolves. EMBL-EBI, through the BioImage Archive, coordinates the maintenance plan, and supports FBbi maintenance alongside GerBI; several of the externally-maintained vocabularies in the set are themselves curated at EMBL-EBI, which simplifies feeding bioimaging requirements upstream.

4. Summary

The work reported here sets out a sustainable arrangement for the selected ontology set: active, community-governed maintenance for FBbi, led by German BioImaging with EMBL-EBI and RIKEN support, and a model of monitoring, periodic review and upstream contribution for the externally-maintained vocabularies that make up the rest of the set. Together with the contribution routes and the per-ontology arrangements summarised in Table 1, this provides a basis for keeping the shared vocabulary usable and current beyond the lifetime of the project, and feeds into the wider project sustainability plan.

5. References

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